

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of AnalaR or G. R. (E. Merck) grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. The kinetic procedure was the same as described earlier².

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by using excess of cerium(IV), which was estimated before and after the completion of the reaction, and the oxidant-substrate mole ratio of 2 : 1 was established.

It was observed that on mixing the reactants, the initial yellow colour of the mixture changed to light red, then to wine red and ultimately deep red. Such change in colour suggested stepwise oxidation of quinol. The reaction mixture containing the organic substrate (1.0 g) was steam-distilled after the oxidation. The yellowish white compound that distilled over was extracted with ether and allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator and identified as *p*-benzoquinone (0.7854 g, 80%), m.p. 116°.

Evidence of free radical formation was obtained from the polymerisation of acrylamide and methyl methacrylate. The reaction mixture containing quinol was allowed to stand with a pinch of acrylamide. It immediately became turbid and within a few hours and the entire reaction mixture turned viscous. This showed that this oxidation takes place through a free radicals mechanism. Positive polymerisation tests were also obtained by using methyl methacrylate as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

The oxidation reaction proceeded satisfactorily at measurable rate in the given range of concentration : $[Ce^{IV}] = 1.08 - 2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[Quinol] = 1.42 - 2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$. But the rate was immeasurable using higher or lower concentration of either of these reactants. The oxidation was second order reaction, being first order with respect to each of the reactants. Any particular run gave linear plot upto about 75% of the reaction. Duplicate rate measurements were reproducible within $\pm 2\%$.

Effect of temperature : The reaction velocity was studied at four different temperatures and the values of kinetic parameters are shown in Table 1.

Kinetics of Oxidation of Quinol by Cerium(IV)

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OXIDATION of quinol by a variety of oxidants has been studied in detail by several investigators¹. A survey of literature showed that no detailed kinetic study was carried out on the oxidation of quinol by cerium(IV) and this is the subject-matter of the present investigation.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON OXIDATION OF QUINOL BY Ce^{IV}

$[Quinol] = 0.0020 M$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 0.0222 M$, $[NaOH] = 0.0033 M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.0000 M$

Temp. K	k_1 $\times 10^4 (\pm 0.01) s^{-1}$	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	PZ $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ J mol ⁻¹	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ J mol ⁻¹	$\Delta E_a^\ddagger$ J mol ⁻¹
298	1.55	-29.6	0.0051	73.8	85.1	
303	3.87	-26.3	0.0051	73.7	84.2	76.3
308	6.97	-25.7	0.0050	73.7	84.2	(mean)
313	9.93	-26.8	0.0049	73.6	84.6	

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Reaction rates were found to increase with temperature. The negative value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and high value of $\Delta F^\ddagger$ indicated that the rate of reaction was immeasurably slow. But the low value of $\Delta E_a^\ddagger$ made the reaction rate measurable.

Inhibiting effect of sulphuric acid: The rate of reaction was found to decrease on increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid (Table 2).

The inhibitory effect observed on increasing the concentration of H_2SO_4 might be due to the formation of the complex species³ which appeared to be the reactive species. Evidence of such a species was obtained from spectral studies⁴. $HCe(SO_4)_3^-$

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SULPHURIC ACID CONCENTRATION ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF QUINOL BY Ce^{IV}

[Quinol]=0.0020 M, $[Ce^{IV}]=0.0222$ M, $[NaOH]=0.0033$ M

$[H_2SO_4]$ (M)	1.50	1.00	0.50	0.25
$k_1 \times 10^4 (\pm 0.02) s^{-1}$	3.20	3.87	9.32	12.11

ion may undergo further protonation in stronger acidic medium,

Mechanism: In the substrate range of $1.42 - 2.50 \times 10^{-3}$ M, the plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{substrate}]$ was linear. This indicated the formation of an intermediate complex between the substrate and the reactive species and showed a Michaelis and Menten type of rate dependence on the substrate concentration. The results of the experimental observations as discussed above clearly showed that *p*-benzoquinone was formed as the oxidation product. The cerium(IV)-organic substrate redox system was found to initiate the polymerisation of acrylamide. This showed the existence of free radical in the reaction sequence. The low values of frequency factor (*PZ*), negative values of entropy of activation etc., all suggested the rigid nature of the activated complex, involving a free radical mechanism as below,

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